

An Enquiry into the Purchase Intention of AI – based Virtual Personal Voice Assistants in India

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Abstract

This paper attempts to analyze the Indian consumers' intention to purchase AI – based virtual personal assistants (VPAs). The various AI beliefs of the Indian consumers were initially captured using forty-four statements via the questionnaire survey method using snowball and convenience sampling techniques. Principal Component factor analysis followed by Varimax rotation was adopted to reduce these statements into nine factors namely: Trust in AI, Knowledge about AI, Personalization Preference, Current usage of AI, Awareness of AI, Positive outlook on Current AI Performance, Future Dangers of AI, Negative outlook on Current AI Performance and Desired Applications of AI. The survey which was conducted across India resulted in a sample size of 637 respondents who did not own a VPA and had either an intention/no intention to purchase a VPA. By employing Independent sample t-tests, the purchase intention was analyzed with respect to the nine reduced factors and the tests were repeated for various demographic profiles like gender, age, annual income and AI knowledge level for a better understanding. The results show that different factors significantly influence the purchase intention for different profiles. A complete understanding of the purchase intention of VPAs with respect to the various dimensions of the consumers' AI beliefs and various demographic profiles is important for both businesses selling VPAs and also for the retail industry as voice shopping via VPAs is the future of e-commerce.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Digital Personal Voice Assistants, Indian Consumer Market, Purchase Intention.

1. Introduction

Transformative disruptions can be fostered via the adoption of artificial intelligence as it leads to enriching human lives by providing assistance, personalization, and automation (Mani et al., 2021). Investments in AI have been growing rapidly; especially giants like Baidu and Google have dominated the investments. The average spending of the tech giants on AI in 2016 can be estimated

as around \$20 to \$30 billion, with nearly 90% on Research and Development and deployment and around 10% on acquisitions in AI (Bughin et al., 2017).

Global IT companies are now investing in virtual personal assistant devices with the rising development in the field of artificial technology (Yang and Lee, 2019). AI assistants will soon revolutionize the way businesses interact with consumers and they would become the primary channel of communication. These assistants would offer convenience and minimize costs and risk for the consumers. There is a rapid colonization of AI assistants in the homes of consumers. For example, 25 million Amazon Echo smart speakers have been sold and it is expected to more than double shortly. Google assistant, another popular AI virtual assistant is available in over 400 million devices. Apple also launched a Siri-enabled Home Pod and Samsung took over Viv, which was founded by Siri's inventors. Tencent and Microsoft also have platforms for their own AI virtual assistants and in China, Xiaoice and Chumenwenwen have over 40 million registered users (Dawar and Bendle, 2018)

The Business-Insider (2017) survey report shows how consumers use Amazon's virtual assistant, Echo. 84.9% set timers, 82.4% play songs, 66% read the news, 61.6% check the time, 60.4% tell a joke, 45.9% control smart lights, 45.3% make shopping lists, 40.9% connect to paid music applications, 36.5% provide traffic information, 32.7% manage a to-do list and 32.1% make purchases on Amazon Prime.

Given the rise of AI enabled digital voice assistants in India and the scope of the business involved, this study aims to enquire into the intention of Indian consumers to purchase these assistants and also analyze the purchase intention in terms of demographics like gender, age, annual income and also the AI knowledge level of the consumers.

2. Literature Review

2.1. AI enabled Digital voice assistants/Conversational agents

Conversational AI refers to the study of techniques employed by software agents which can interact with humans naturally in the form of conversations. Examples of these conversational agents include: Google Assistant, Apple's Siri, Amazon Alexa, etc. First generation of these conversational agents mainly communicated about short, task related dialogs like requesting information or playing music rather than longer conversation which are free-form in nature. The next generation of conversational agents needs to aim at having engaging and sustained dialog with the consumers (Ram et al., 2018).

"AI voice-assistant is an AI engine and voice recognition-based voice recognition that collects and provides customized information to users, including sending email, scheduling, and restaurant reservations according to the user's voice commands" (p.3, Joon-Hwan Kim, 2021). The in-home voice assistants have been designed to be more

human-like performing several daily life tasks like purchasing items, setting alarms, looking up recipes, offering customized information, turning lights on and off, understanding a user's schedule, etc (McLean and Osei-Frimpong, 2019).

The research into AI based digital assistants' dates back to 1966 when Joseph Weizenbaum came up with the famous ELIZA. Parallely, the technology giants like Amazon, Microsoft, Google, and IBM have been working on advancing the AI-based digital assistants in order to make them more suited to the mass market. The AI-based digital assistants elevate the performance of human tasks with more intelligence and interactivity compared to other traditional software applications. These assistants receive input via conversational user interface like speech, text or even computer vision and deliver the output via natural language processing. They process and represent the domain knowledge and also develop new knowledge based on the data collected using machine learning algorithms (Maedche et al., 2019). Among the various AI attributes, consumers recognize speech recognition as the most important. This conversation function of AI devices makes them more valuable and social. They are now able to not only carry out orders but also be social and understanding of the user's needs and moods and thereby make friendly conversations (Joon-Hwan Kim, 2021). The AI enabled consumer devices which are mainly products integrated with AI come in two forms: smart speakers and smart display. Smart speakers are voice activated AI devices which execute tasks and offer oral responses to queries of the consumers. Smart displays which were introduced in 2018 are also voice activated and provide both visual and oral responses to queries (Manis, 2020).

The routine usage of digital voice assistants by consumers have been on the increase. Based on the survey of 26,000 consumers in 26 countries, nearly 84% of 14- to 17-year-old teenagers are interested in or are currently using the voice-enabled digital assistants in their smartphones. In every age category, nearly one third of the consumers are also interested in this feature. India (55%), China (55%) and USA (46%) are the high usage countries for this feature whereas Canada (27%) and Germany (28%) are the low usage countries. The stand-alone digital voice assistants are now currently used by the early adopters but most of these early adopters are using them on a daily basis. This kind of pervasive usage would result in advocacy. This trend in the adoption pattern represents a more positive cycle as it represents a more enthusiastic trend compared to the trends of other new product categories released lately (Accenture, 2017).

Digital voice assistants like Google Home and Amazon Alexa have redefined the entire shopping experience (Bughin et al., 2017). Voice shopping via these voice assistants is a new shopping channel providing personalized services and at the same time warrants consumers to entrust a lot of their personal preferences and information to the AI voice assistant companies and the voice shopping service providers (Bawack et al., 2021). Google Home has partnered with nearly 50 Google express retailers like

PetSmart, Costco and WholeFoods and on the other hand, Alexa has partnered with over 100 third party services in order to complete customers' purchase orders. These digital assistants are also able to spot preferences based on the videos and images liked online by the consumers. The latest digital assistant by Amazon, the new Echo Look device integrates computer vision and machine learning by incorporating a camera into the virtual assistant function of Alexa. It suggests styles depending on the user's body shape and wardrobe (Bughin et al., 2017). Many brands use the voice assistants to convey brand related services and information to the consumers. Consumers also engage with brands through these voice assistants via the technology, situational and AI attributes which drive this engagement. The AI attributes of perceived intelligence, social presence and social attraction mainly influence this engagement (McLean et al., 2021).

Thus these AI voice assistants engage the consumer immensely via social interactions by offering personalized experiences and thereby form affective, cognitive and behavioral relations with the consumers. (McLean et al., 2021). Consumers would be satisfied with voice assistants and continue to use them when they are able to control, focus and engage in their interactions with these voice assistants. Voice assistants need to incorporate sincerity, functional intelligence, and creativity by providing effective, sincere, current, honest, and efficient information in order to achieve this consumer empowerment (Poushneh, 2021).

2.2. Purchase Intention of AI virtual assistants

The cognitive engagement between the consumer and the machine is mainly influenced by factors grouped into agent-related, usage-related, user-related, evaluation and attitude related factors. The usage-related factors include the factors involved in the processes and outcomes, like the perceived usefulness, for example. The agent-related factors involve the factors associated with the characteristics of the agent (AI device) like the visual appearance of the AI device (agent). Similarly; the user-related factors include the factors related to the users' characteristics like gender, innovativeness, etc. Evaluation and attitude related factors include the evaluation of the agent and the attitude of the user (Ling et al., 2021).

Consumers' willingness to pay for innovations like the AI devices is also measured by the variable IWTPi which is inert willingness to pay for innovations. IWTPi is positively influenced by financial expectations, income and significance of status symbols and negatively influenced by stress avoidance and savings orientation (Frank et al., 2015). The purchase intention of AI devices among the consumers is mainly influenced by the enjoyment factor (Yang and Lee, 2019) derived from the hedonic aspects of AI devices (Manis, 2020) followed by other factors like: subjective norms, perceived value and ease of use (Sohn and Kwon, 2020). The enjoyment factor in turn depends on content quality and visual attractiveness of the virtual personal assistants

(Yang and Lee, 2019). Subjective norms imply that social factors play an important role in the purchase decision of AI devices and the opinion of peers are important in the AI adoption decision owing to the shortage of practical use experience. High perceived value indicates high expectations among the consumers about the AI devices. The interest in technology is one of the main factors influencing the acceptance of AI devices, which are highly innovative with less practical value (Sohn and Kwon, 2020). Among the various factors influencing the adoption of these AI virtual personal assistants, the perceived enjoyment is more influential when compared to the perceived usefulness. Hence companies must advance the design of these assistants so that they deliver more hedonic value instead of utilitarian value (Yang and Lee, 2019).

The adoption of digital voice assistants is primarily influenced by the functional elements like perceived usefulness (Yang and Lee, 2019); by relational elements like trust and rapport; and by social elements like perceived social presence (Fernandes and Oliveira, 2021). The consumers' acceptance of these artificially intelligent conversational agents is driven mainly by usage benefits which are in turn driven by the characteristics of the user and the agent. The usage benefits are the extent to which the user derives benefits from using these conversational agents. These benefits include symbolic, hedonic and utilitarian. (Ling et al., 2021). The use of in-home voice assistants is motivated by symbolic benefits, social benefits and utilitarian benefits offered by these assistants. The social benefits refer to the natural human-like interactions which voice assistants' offer. The utilitarian benefits refer to the utilitarian tasks like assistance in completing tasks, seeking support, searching for information, and processing orders which voice assistants perform. The symbolic benefits imply the usage of voice assistants for reaffirming one's social status (McLean and Osei-Frimpong, 2019).

The acceptance of artificially intelligent (AI) devices by the consumers could be explained by a three-stage model. During the first stage of acceptance, which is the primary appraisal stage, the adoption of AI devices is influenced by hedonic motivation, group norms, social networks, and anthropomorphism. During the next stage of secondary appraisal, the emotion towards the usage of AI device is determined based on the evaluation of effort and performance expectancies. In the final outcome stage, the behavioral intention towards AI devices is determined based on the emotions of the consumers (Gursoy et al., 2019).

3. Sample and Methodology

The Indian consumers staying all over India and having knowledge about online e-commerce communication was taken as the population for this study. Data collection was administered via the questionnaire survey method and the survey was executed via Google forms application. Snow-ball sampling and convenience sampling were adopted in order to identify the sample as the sample was from a hard-to-reach population. Consumers residing in the major metropolitan cities of Mumbai, Delhi,

Kolkata, Bangalore, Chennai, Hyderabad, Cochin and Pune were all respondents of the survey. The number of total valid questionnaires obtained was 1028. Out of the 1028 respondents, 391 respondents already owned a virtual personal assistant (VPA) and were hence removed from the sample. The balance of 637 respondents formed the sample of the study.

4. Results and Analysis

The main objective of the study was to analyze the influence on the decision to purchase AI personal voice assistants. The main factors which influence the purchase intention were first derived from fifty statements which were then reduced to forty-four and loaded onto nine factors using Principal Component Factor Analysis followed by Varimax rotation. Only the factors which had a factor loading of more than 0.5 and an Eigen value of more than 1 were taken. Each of the factors derived were named based on the variables composing each factor. The derived factors have a cumulative percentage of 63.359% indicating that the factors explain a variation of nearly one sigma level (as shown in Table 1). The factors were also reliable as the Cronbach alpha of each of the factors was more than 0.5.

Table 1: Factors derived via Principal Component Factor Analysis

S.No	Factor	Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
		Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	Trust in AI	5.103	11.341	11.341
2	Knowledge about AI	4.172	9.270	20.611
3	Personalization Preference	3.607	8.016	28.627
4	Current Usage of AI	3.162	7.026	35.653
5	Awareness of AI	2.992	6.650	42.303
6	Positive outlook on Current AI Performance	2.846	6.324	48.627
7	Future Dangers of AI	2.407	5.349	53.976
8	Negative outlook on Current AI Performance	2.292	5.094	59.069
9	Desired Applications of AI	1.930	4.289	63.359

In order to determine the influence of the derived factors on the purchase decision of the consumers, Independent sample t tests were used.

Independent sample t-test compares the means of the two groups divided based on their intention to purchase AI virtual personal assistants (VPAs). Independent sample t -tests compared the means of each of the derived factors between the groups which have the intention and which do not have the intention. The p-value was significant only for the following factors:

- Trust in AI (p-value: 0.038)
- Personalization Preference (p-value:0.000)

- Current usage of AI (p-value:0.000)
- Positive outlook on Current AI Performance(p-value:0.0005)
- Desired Applications of AI(p-value: 0.019)

The results of the Independent sample t-tests are summarized and tabulated in the Table 2 below. The results indicate that for the significant relationships, the mean of the significant factor of the group with the purchase intention was higher than the mean of the group without the intention. Hence the consumers who have the intention to purchase the AI VPAs are those who have higher trust in AI, who have a higher preference for personalization, who currently use AI applications, who have a better positive outlook about AI and who desire several AI applications in the future.

Table 2: Independent Sample t-test results

S.No	Factor	Mean		t-value	p-value for one tail test
		With Intention	Without Intention		
1	Trust in AI	0.031872	-0.10769	1.780	0.038
2	Knowledge about AI	-0.008364	-0.13521	1.582	0.057
3	Personalization Preference	0.1624546	-0.20737	4.722	0.000
4	Current Usage of AI	0.0188798	-0.37086	5.218	0.000
5	Awareness of AI	-0.035655	-0.02319	-0.165	0.4345
6	Positive outlook on Current AI Performance	0.1034238	-0.16643	3.354	0.0005
7	Future Dangers of AI	-0.008855	0.0107173	-0.259	0.398
8	Negative outlook on Current AI Performance	0.0158646	0.100591	-1.090	0.138
9	Desired Applications of AI	0.0394501	-0.12681	2.078	0.019

The Independent sample t-tests were repeated for different demographic profiles in order to further describe the consumers who intent to purchase the AI VPAs.

The first profiling was in terms of gender. 269 consumers were male and 368 were female consumers. Based on the significant factors shown in Table 3, the male consumers, who have the intention to purchase the AI VPAs are those who have higher trust in AI VPAs and higher preference for personalization, who currently use more AI applications, and those who have a more positive outlook on the current AI performance. For the female consumers, the same results hold true except that trust does not play a significant role in their purchase decision.

Table 3: Independent sample t-test results – Gender Profile

S.No	Factor	Male Consumers			Female Consumers		
		Mean		p-value for one tail test	Mean		p-value for one tail test
		With Intent	Without Intent		With Intent	Without Intent	
1	AI Trust	0.14295	-0.06411	0.049	-0.070	-0.13299	0.2685
2	AI Knowledge	0.06288	0.05242	0.465	-0.074	-0.24412	0.0595
3	Personalization Preference	0.13969	-0.26263	0.002	0.1834	-0.17529	0.000
4	Usage of AI applications	-0.0127	-0.41587	0.001	0.0479	-0.34474	0.000
5	AI Awareness	0.03604	0.05562	0.4345	-0.102	-0.06893	0.371
6	Positive outlook on Current AI Performance	0.10267	-0.16323	0.0205	0.1041	-0.16828	0.0045
7	Future Dangers of AI	-0.0603	0.08973	0.1005	0.0385	-0.03515	0.2315
8	Negative outlook on Current AI Performance	0.12496	0.13705	0.461	-0.085	0.079427	0.053
9	Future Applications of AI	0.12007	-0.09027	0.056	-0.035	-0.148	0.1305

The next analysis was in terms of the age profile. Young consumers in the age group of 25 years and below were 144. There were 273 middle aged consumers in the age bracket of 26 to 45 years and 220 elderly consumers above 45 years. Young consumers who have the purchase intention tend to have more trust in AI and use more AI applications. Middle-aged consumers who have more personalization preference and use more AI applications have a positive outlook on the present AI performance and who desire several AI applications in the future tend to purchase AI VPAs. Older consumers however rely on trust and personalization preference to make the purchase decision.

Table 4: Independent sample t-test results – Age Profile

S.No	Factor	Young Consumers			Middle-aged Consumers			Old Consumers		
		Mean		p-value for one tail test	Mean		p-value for one tail test	Mean		p-value for one tail test
		With Intention	Without Intention		With Intention	Without Intention		With Intention	Without Intention	
1	AI Trust	-0.001	-0.3005	0.027	-0.073	0.04905	0.168	0.205	-0.1942	0.001
2	AI Knowledge	0.0859	0.2219	0.193	0.045	-0.0719	0.172	-0.165	-0.3771	0.066
3	Personalization Preference	0.2204	0.1558	0.335	0.075	-0.2645	0.003	0.231	-0.3152	0.000
4	Usage of AI applications	0.0945	-0.5221	0.000	0.067	-0.3626	0.000	-0.114	-0.3083	0.069
5	AI Awareness	-0.088	-0.0224	0.342	-0.075	0.09299	0.068	0.065	-0.1557	0.051
6	Positive outlook on Current AI Performance	0.1937	0.1075	0.277	0.206	-0.2859	0.000	-0.118	-0.1609	0.382
7	Future Dangers of AI	0.0027	0.1116	0.236	0.103	0.15708	0.326	-0.173	-0.2037	0.402
8	Negative outlook on Current AI Performance	-0.137	0.0304	0.146	0.091	0.08689	0.486	0.048	0.14959	0.219
9	Future Applications of AI	-0.062	0.0144	0.328	0.012	-0.2852	0.008	0.167	-0.0139	0.096

The next profiling was done based on the annual income. 283 consumers with an income of Rs. 4 lakhs and below are termed as low-income consumers. 178 consumers belonged to the mediocre category with an income of Rs. 4.01 to 10 lakhs. And 176 consumers belonged to the high-income level of more than 10 lakhs. The purchase intention of low-income consumers depends on personalization preference and present AI usage and those who have a positive(negative) outlook on the present AI performance have(don't have) the purchase intention. The purchase intention of the average income consumers has the same influences and they also have the desire for AI applications in the future. However, the high-income consumers who have the intention are only those who currently use AI applications.

Table 5: Independent sample t-test results – Income Profile

S.No	Factor	Low Annual Income			Mediocre Annual Income			High Annual Income		
		Mean		p-value for one tail test	Mean		p-value for one tail test	Mean		p-value for one tail test
		With Intention	Without Intention		With Intention	Without Intention		With Intention	Without Intention	
1	AI Trust	-0.032	-0.0907	0.297	-0.122	-0.2169	0.278	0.229	0.0102	0.08
2	AI Knowledge	-0.146	-0.2289	0.241	0.099	-0.1449	0.052	0.091	0.0698	0.44
3	Personalization Preference	0.2480	-0.1625	0.000	0.251	-0.2544	0.001	-0.01	-0.2334	0.08
4	Usage of AI applications	-0.010	-0.3991	0.000	-0.007	-0.3558	0.004	0.077	-0.3344	0.01
5	AI Awareness	-0.186	-0.0625	0.141	-0.071	-0.1175	0.376	0.186	0.1888	0.49
6	Positive outlook on Current AI Performance	0.1167	-0.1540	0.009	0.219	-0.1510	0.009	0.001	-0.2133	0.10
7	Future Dangers of AI	-0.027	-0.0312	0.486	0.038	-0.0146	0.356	-0.02	0.1316	0.16
8	Negative outlook on Current AI Performance	-0.133	0.0823	0.027	0.088	0.13002	0.393	0.157	0.0969	0.35
9	Future Applications of AI	-0.049	-0.1501	0.196	0.043	-0.2237	0.044	0.152	0.0560	0.28

The last profiling was done in terms of the AI Knowledge level. 238 consumers had low AI knowledge level, 244 consumers had mediocre and 155 consumers had high AI knowledge level. In the low AI knowledge category, the purchase intention depends on trust, knowledge, personalization preference and current usage of AI. In the average AI knowledge profile, personalization preference, current usage, positive outlook on AI and desire for futuristic AI applications influence the purchase intention. In the high knowledge category, current usage and positive outlook on the AI performance alone determine the purchase intention.

Table 6: Independent sample t-test results – AI Knowledge Profile

S.No	Factor	Low AI Knowledge			Mediocre AI Knowledge			High AI Knowledge		
		Mean		p-value for one tail test	Mean		p-value for one tail test	Mean		p-value for one tail test
		With Intent	Without Intent		With Intent	Without Intent		With Intent	Without Intent	
1	AI Trust	-0.00	-0.254	0.03	-0.088	-0.0893	0.496	0.2617	0.1699	0.276
2	AI Knowledge	-0.08	-0.336	0.03	0.0034	-0.0869	0.255	0.0533	0.2093	0.137
3	Personalization Preference	0.380	-0.328	0.00	0.051	-0.17292	0.037	0.1005	-0.0095	0.263
4	Usage of AI applications	-0.15	-0.541	0.00	-0.071	-0.30976	0.029	0.3371	-0.1107	0.001
5	AI Awareness	-0.04	-0.097	0.33	-0.036	-0.12131	0.239	-0.028	0.2886	0.021
6	Positive outlook on Current AI Performance	-0.02	-0.113	0.24	0.2358	-0.13709	0.002	0.0261	-0.3266	0.016
7	Future Dangers of AI	0.089	-0.000	0.22	-0.025	0.00299	0.413	-0.091	0.0469	0.196
8	Negative outlook on Current AI Performance	0.195	0.025	0.11	-0.063	0.19262	0.015	-0.056	0.1124	0.155
9	Future Applications of AI	-0.12	-0.124	0.48	0.223	-0.12418	0.006	-0.079	-0.1379	0.348

In order to further describe the consumers who intent to purchase the AI VPAs, the demographic characteristics of these consumers are tabulated below in Table 7. The table clearly shows that the majority of the consumers who intent to purchase AI VPAs are female consumers who are below 35 years of age. Both the low (30.4%) and the high (32.9%) income consumers express intention to purchase AI. The majorities of the consumers who express intent to purchase AI have a moderate AI knowledge level of 3 and have interacted with AI in the past.

Table 7: Demographic Profile of Consumers who intent to purchase AI VPAs

Demographic Dimension		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative %
Gender	Male	150	47.9	47.9
	Female	163	52.1	100
Age	25 and below	85	27.2	27.2
	26 to 35 years	83	26.5	53.7
	36 to 45 years	49	15.7	69.3
	46 to 55 years	36	11.5	80.8
	Above 55 years	60	19.2	100
Annual Income	Rs. 2 lakhs and below	95	30.4	30.4
	Rs.2.01 to 4 lakhs	39	12.5	42.8
	Rs. 4.01 to 6 lakhs	31	9.9	52.7
	Rs. 6.01 to 8 lakhs	18	5.8	58.5
	Rs. 8.01 to 10 lakhs	27	8.6	67.1
	More than Rs.10 lakhs	103	32.9	100
AI Knowledge Level	Level 1	29	9.3	9.3
	Level 2	64	20.4	29.7
	Level 3	134	42.8	72.5
	Level 4	73	23.3	95.8
	Level 5	13	4.2	100
Interaction with AI	Yes	188	60.1	60.1
	No	84	26.8	86.9
	Not sure	41	13.1	100

Conclusion

In India, the AI enabled virtual personal assistants (VPAs) are in infancy stage and businesses are keen to know the consumers' intention to purchase these VPAs as they are the future of e-commerce. This research is based on the survey of Indian consumers residing across India wherein data was collected via the questionnaire survey method using snowball and convenience sampling techniques. Independent sample t-test was adopted to analyze the consumers' intention to purchase VPAs with respect to nine factors derived from forty-four statements which captured the consumers' beliefs about AI. The results showed that the consumers who have the intention to purchase the AI VPAs are those who have higher trust in AI, who have a higher preference for personalization, who currently use AI applications, who have a better positive outlook about AI and who desire several AI applications in the future. The analysis was further deepened by dividing the sample into various demographic profiles like gender, age, annual income, and AI knowledge level. Various factors were also found to be significant for a different demographic profile. The demographic profile of the consumers who intend to purchase AI VPAs was also explained. The results of the study would be useful to businesses selling VPAs as they can have a clear picture of their target customer base. VPAs are the future of e-commerce and voice shopping is the next big step in the retail industry. Being the channel of future business, VPAs play an important role and the knowledge of the consumers' intention to purchase these VPAs become very important.

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